

Vibration Analysis on Passive Viscoelastic Constrained Layer Damping for Plates

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Abstract – The machines and structures are treated with Conventional passive constrained layer damping (PCLD) owing to their reliability and simplicity. In order to reduce vibration, plastics are used as major components in industrial structural design. Rubber has a special tendency such as elastic and viscous in nature. Rubber materials can be act as shock and vibration isolators. In this research Butyl rubber is viscoelastic material which is acting as the damping layer, steel and aluminium patches are used as constrained layer. Here, change in length of patch and size of constrained layer and damping layer is varied for constant length and thickness of base layer. The size of patches and number of patches are varied for different locations. Aluminium and steel constrained layer are considers as a specimens for the study. Damping characteristics of plates are determined by experimentally and analytically by using FFT analyzer and ANSYS software respectively.

Keywords: Vibration Damping, CLD, Modulus of Constraining Layer.

I. Introduction

Almost all Engineering structures experience vibrational motion [1]. The methods to increase damping can be categorized into two categories: passive damping and active damping. Active and semi-active damping treatment has been slow due to high costs and complexity. [2]Passive damping as a well-developed technique, in general, is more simple and cost-effective. [3]To control vibration, the Passive damping technology is employed with viscoelastic materials. [5]The steel industry proposes damped sandwich sheets in which a thin layer of viscoelastic material is sandwiched between two elastic face layers.

Ross, et.al developed a three-layer model to predict damping in plates with constrained layer damping treatments [8]. TianXiong Liu, et.al was the first to present a theoretical approach of damped thin structures with a constrained viscoelastic layer [9]. Kerwin, E.M found that the shear motion of the plates due to energy dissipation mechanism[4] . To improve damping performance of structures, damping materials can be sandwiched in passive damping technology [6]. Lot of research has been carried out over the last few decades to either alter existing materials, or develop entirely new materials to improve the structural dynamics of components to which a damping material could be applied [7].

The main focus of this paper is to study the effect of constraining layer parameters in damping effects using method of passive viscoelastic constrained layer damping

technology experimentally and analytically using finite element method.

II. Modeling and Properties

II.1. Modeling Plates using FEM

Plates are modeled by using Solid Brick 8node 45 Element used in ANSYS Software.

TABLE I
SPECIMEN DIMENSIONS

S.No.,	Material Type	Dimension of plate in mm
1	Base layer	356X356X2
2	Damping layer	356X356X1.5
3	Constraining layer	356X356X1

II.2. Geometrical Property of Plate

Totally 13 specimens are prepared, in that 6 specimen for aluminium constraining layer, other 6 specimen for steel constraining layer and single specimen for bare plate. The size of viscoelastic layer and constraining layer for plates are varied as follows

Fig. 1 Geometry of plate with viscoelastic core

TABLE 2
NUMBER OF PATCHES

Dimension of constrained layer and damping layer in mm	No., of damping layer patches	No., of constraining layer patches for steel	No., of constraining layer patches for aluminium
72X72	18	9	9
51X71	12	6	6
356X356	2	1	1
120X120	2	1	1
52X52	18	9	9

TABLE 3
MATERIAL PROPERTIES

S.No.,	Material Type	Young's Modulus(E) [MPa]	Density(ρ) [kg/m ³]	Poisson's Ratio
1	Steel Plate	210X10 ³	7850	0.3
2	Aluminium Plate	70X10 ³	2700	0.35
3	Butyl Rubber	8.3378	1250	0.0

III. Experimental Setup

Specimens are prepared as given in above Table 1. These specimens are glued by using Araldite resin. Initially the specimens are prepared for required dimensions and then clamped in the fixture. The FFT analyzer is connected to the accelerometer and impact hammer. The accelerometer fixed at specified point on plate as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 Wireframe Geometry Creation

The impact hammer is stricken at specified point, from this amplitude and displacement values are measured. These obtained values are transferred to PC and graphs are plotted for comparisons by using FFT software.

Four points are marked in the plate as shown in Fig. 2, at that particular point the force is applied by impact hammer and amplitude measured by accelerometer. The point where force is applied is called drive point. The point where accelerometer is fixed is called response point.

IV. Results and Discussions

Modal analysis and harmonic analysis are done for plates using ANSYS software. These results are compared with one another. Figure 3 and Figure 4 gives the linear comparison graph for aluminium and steel CLD patches. From these graph modes are identified. Bare plate gives the high modes than other CLD patches.

Fig. 3 Linear Comparison Graph For Steel CLD

Fig. 4 Linear Comparison Graph For Aluminium CLD

Fig. 5 Log Magnitude Comparison for Aluminium CLD Patches

Fig. 6 Log Magnitude Comparison for Steel CLD Patches

Fig. 5 and Figure 6 shows amplitude and frequency graph of log magnitude for aluminium and steel CLD patches. This shows that fully CLD patches have high damping than other CLD patches.

V. Conclusion

From the obtained FEA results, the damping factor is high for steel plates compared with aluminium plates. Then, fully CLD steel patch has high damping and next to that single patch and five patches have high damping. The amplitude of plate is minimum so that vibration will be reduced. The experimental results are yet to be taken and predicted to get similar results.

References

- [1] Anne-Sophie Plouin and Etienne Balmes, "A Test Model of Plates with Constrained Viscoelastic Materials".
- [2] C. Chantalakhana and R. Stanway "Active Constrained Layer Damping of Clamped-Clamped Plate Vibrations" Journal of Sound and Vibration (2001) 241(5), 755-777.
- [3] Jones, D. I. G. 2001. Handbook of Viscoelastic Vibration Damping. West Sussex, England: John Wiley and Sons, LTD., Nashif A.D.
- [4] Kerwin, E.M. 1959. Damping of flexural waves by a constrained viscoelastic layer. Journal of the Acoustical Society of America, 31(7), 952-962.
- [5] Kripa K. Varanasi and Samir A. Nayfeh Damping of Flexural Vibration by Low-Density Foams and Granular Materials" 2003 ASME Design Engineering Technical Conferences.
- [6] M. Ruzzene and j. Oh, "Finite Element Modelling of Magnetic Constrained Layer Damping" Journal of Sound and Vibration (2000) 236(4), 657-682.
- [7] Park, Jin-Tack and Choi, Nak-Sam, Flexural Vibration Analysis of a Sandwich Beam Specimen with a Partially Inserted Viscoelastic Layer, KSME International Journal, Vol. 18 No. 3, 2004, pp. 347-356.
- [8] Ross, D., Ungar, E., and Kerwin, E., 1959, "Damping of Flexural Vibrations by Means of Viscoelastic Laminate," Structural Damping, ASME, New York.
- [9] TianXiong Liu , Hong Xing Hua and Zhiyi Zhang "Robust control of plate vibration via active constrained layer damping" Thin-Walled Structures 42 (2004) 427-448.